

THE PROTECTED AREAS IN BULGARIA

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Summary. A short review of the protected area in Bulgaria, and the main problems in their management and protection are presented.

Key Words. National parks, reserves, Natura 2000, protection, Bulgaria.

INTRODUCTION

Protected areas are a concept of human society for conserving wild nature. They are of great importance to sustain ecosystem services and to treasure evolutionary heritage of life on Earth. A well-developed system of protected areas is critical for maintaining of natural resources in response to the rapid environmental change. According to the definition of IUCN, the International Union for Conservation of Nature definition (Dudley, 2008): "A *protected area is a clearly defined geographical space, recognised, dedicated and managed, through legal or other effective means, to achieve the long term conservation of nature with associated ecosystem services and cultural values*". Over the last decades, the number of protected areas has increased up to 15.4% of the Earth's terrestrial area (outside Antarctica) and amounts to 3.4% of its marine area (IUCN and UNEP-WCMC 2014). Despite the increase, the protected areas' coverage is still low.

IUCN developed a system of 6 categories of protected areas, defined by their management objectives (Dudley, 2008). Common framework helps provide international uniformity and enable comparative analysis of the global

protected areas' system (Worboys et al., 2015). The framework of the categories is supported by almost all nations within the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (2004) as well as by other nations.

Bulgaria established a system of protected areas (Fig. 1) in accordance with its natural resources and needs, and in compliance with the national and the European legislation, as well as with other international obligations.

BIODIVERSITY IN BULGARIA

The Republic of Bulgaria has a territory of 110,910 km² within which a rich biological diversity and various natural habitats from 3 biogeographic regions - Alpine, Continental and Black Sea - are found. Bulgaria is identified as one of Europe's most biodiversity rich countries. Its geographic location, the altitudinal range from 0 to 2,925.4 m and the highly varied climatic influences in the different regions of the country favour the existence of 97 mammal species, 409 birds, 37 reptiles, 19 amphibians, 219 Black Sea and

Figure 1. A map of protected areas in Bulgaria.

freshwater fish species, above 30,000 insects and other invertebrate species. There are 4,100 vascular plant species, 3,100 algae, 754 bryophytes and 4,900 fungi and fungus-like organisms (Fifth National Report on Biodiversity, Bulgaria 2009-2013). The specificity of Bulgaria's biodiversity is defined by the presence of a large number of endemic species and subspecies. The plant endemic species amount to approximately 11% of the entire flora - quite a big share compared to other larger European countries. The available information on invertebrate taxa show that 8.8% of the Bulgarian non-insect species and 4.3% of the insects are endemic. Almost all of the main habitat types represented in Europe can be found in Bulgaria and there are 96 habitats registered in Bulgaria only (Biodiversity Support Program, 1994).

FIRST STEPS IN WILD NATURE CONSERVATION IN BULGARIA

Nature conservation efforts in Bulgaria started in the first years of the 20th century with acts on forestry, hunting and fishing. However, the modern concept of territory protection in Bulgaria was established by founding of the "Union for Protection of Native Nature", a joint association by various nature science societies, within in 1928. With the impetus given by the scientific environmental union, Bulgaria's initial protected areas were gradually established in the 1930's. In 1931, "Hrastevo" near Devin (Rhodopes Mountain) was proclaimed as a strictly guarded area for the protection of relict *Pinus nigra* J.F. Arnold forests. In 1933, the first officially declared protected area in Bulgaria was decreed - "Gorna Elenitsa-Silkosia" reserve in Strandzha Mountain. Its area of 396 ha was designated to protect the evergreen shrub formations in the water catchment area of Veleka river. Shortly thereafter, the reserves of "Parangalitsa" in Rila Mountain (1933), "Bayovi dupki", "Dunino kuche" and "Banski suhodol" in Pirin Mountain (1934) were proclaimed. On October 27th, 1934 the first state park – the People's Park of "Vitosha" - was decreed. It is also the first nature protection park on the Balkan Peninsula. In 1936 an act on "protection of mother nature" was decreed by Boris III, Tsar of Bulgaria (<http://www.ekoarhiv.bg/dokumenti/naredba-zakon-za-zashtita-na-rodната-priroda>).

According to the Register of protected areas in Bulgaria, currently the protected areas under the national Protected Territories' Act cover 5.4% of the country's total territory and predominantly consists of forest lands. This share is significantly smaller than the average for the other European countries – 12%. Although Bulgaria's Protected Areas System under the national Biodi-

versity Act (implementing the EU environmental network Natura 2000 in Bulgaria) covers about 33% of the country, it lacks both management plans and management bodies and has so far limited practical meaning, Natura 2000 still being regarded as a network of “paper parks”.

LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF PROTECTED AREAS IN BULGARIA

Legally, the protected areas in Bulgaria fall within the 2 categories, outlined above. They are either designated under the Protected Territories Act (1998) as national objects of protection and management or under the Biological Diversity Act (2002) as protected areas (sites) within the European environmental network Natura 2000.

The Protected Territories Act “*regulates the categories of protected areas, the assigned use thereof and the regime of protection and use, designation and management*”. The national protected areas are managed in accordance with the Act, the designation order for their establishment and their management plan (not elaborated for all Bulgarian protected areas, yet). The authority responsible for the management and control on the Protected Territories Act is the Ministry of Environment and Water, supplemented by its subsidiary the Executive Environment Agency and the Directorates of National and Nature parks (the directorates of National Parks are subsidiaries of the Ministry of Environment and Water but the directorates of the 11 Nature Parks are subsidiaries of the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forests). The Protected Territories Act has adopted six categories of protection that generally adhere to those of the IUCN: reserve, national park, natural monument, managed nature reserve, nature park and protected site. Until the end of 2015, 1,014 protected areas have been declared under this Act.

Reserves

Bulgarian reserves correspond to the protected areas within IUCN's category Ia (Strict Nature Reserves). There are 55 reserves in the Republic of Bulgaria covering an area of 77,064.9 ha. Most of the reserves are in forest ecosystems and over 60% of their area is part of the 3 Bulgarian National Parks. Reserves are strictly protected areas containing representative natural ecosystems and habitats of rare species and they are important for scientific research and long-term environmental monitoring. All human activities within the reserves that may damage the original natural features are banned.

Figure 2. Pirin National Park, Bulgaria.

Figure 3. Natural Park “Rilski Manastir”, Bulgaria.

Figure 4. Strandzha Park, Bulgaria.

Figure 5. Belasitsa Park, Bulgaria.

National Parks

They contain natural or near natural ecosystems with a wide variety of species and habitats of characteristic and unique landscapes and natural monuments, and correspond to the IUCN's protected areas category II. National Parks' specific objectives are: protection of biodiversity along with promoting education and recreation (Dudley, 2008). Settlements and construction are not permitted within their territory. Three national parks with an area of 193 423 ha were declared in Bulgaria - "Rila", "Pirin" and "Central Balkan".

The three National Parks cover 1.74% of the country's territory. The land within the National Parks is exclusive state property.

"Rila" National Park is the largest park in the country and one of the largest protected areas in Europe with an area of 78,040 ha (Management plan of the National Park "Rila", 2014-2024). It is located in the central and highest parts of Rila Mountain and boasts the highest peak on the Balkans - Musala (2,925.4 m). The park is inhabited by about 4,186 invertebrate and 238 vertebrate species. Among the invertebrates, 280 endemic species and subspecies, 261 relict taxa and 44 species threatened with extinction have been established. At that park 184 vertebrates species are with conservation importance. There are 1,651 vascular plant species. Almost 66% of its territory is populated by magnificent coniferous trees such as spruce *Picea abies* (L.) H.Karst., white pine *Pinus sylvestris* L., Macedonian pine *Pinus peuce* Griseb. and silver fir *Abies alba* Mill.. Near 120 natural lakes, most of which of glacial origin are among the most notable attractions in the park. The reserves within "Rila" National Park are four: "Parangalitsa", "Central Rila Reserve", "Ibar" and "Skakavitsa".

"Pirin" National Park (Fig. 2) is a part of Pirin Mountain and covers an area of 40,356 ha (Management plan for the National Park "Pirin", 2014-2024). More than 50 peaks over 2,500 meters fall within the park with the highest one, Vihren (2,914 m), ranking third highest on the Balkans. The mountain is rich in lake cirques with about 180 glacial lakes. "Pirin" National Park is the centre of speciation and a refuge for glacial relict species. The unique character of the mountain is formed by rocky habitats and coniferous forests of two endemic species - Macedonian pine *Pinus peuce* Griseb. and Bosnian pine *Pinus heldreichii* H.Christ. One of the oldest tree in Bulgaria, the Bosnian pine "Baykusheva" aged over 1,300 years, is located in "Pirin" National Park, too. A significant part of the recorded invertebrate species (nearly 3,000 species) are of conservation importance as endemics (228), relicts (176) and rare (300) species. Among these, 18 species are listed on the World and European Red lists. The park is inhabited by approximately 250 vertebrate species, in-

cluding many rare and endangered species. Two strict reserves (according to the Protected Territories Act's classification) - "Bayuvi Dupki-Dzindziritsa" and "Yulen" - fall within "Pirin" National Park. Due to its unique natural landscape and high conservation importance, in 1983 "Pirin" National Park became one of the UNESCO's World Heritage Sites and in 1998 was designated as a CORINE Site.

"Central Balkan" National Park lies in the centre of Bulgaria and occupies the highest parts of the Balkan range with a total area of 72,021 ha (Management plan for the National Park "Central Balkan", 2014-2024). It stretches 85 km in length and has an average width of 10 km, treasuring a unique wealth of plant and animal species. The most typical forest tree in the "Central Balkan" is the common beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) which forms the largest uniform beech massive in Europe of about 60,000 ha. The park provides habitats for a great variety of plants - more than half of the species known for Bulgaria - and the presence of 11 local, 10 Bulgarian and 67 Balkan endemic species, 30 species under the protection of the Biodiversity Act, 81 ones included in the Red Book of Bulgaria, 9 - in the Red list of Europe and 10 threatened species on IUCN's list. 2,387 species and subspecies of invertebrates have been established in the park, including 261 rare (stenotopic) species, 168 endemic species, 108 relict species and 36 species from the world and the European lists of endangered species (IUCN (19), CORINE (21) and according to the Bulgarian Biodiversity Act (10). Over the last 30 years, more than 300 species of vertebrates were identified in the park: 6 species of fish, 8 species of amphibians, 14 reptile species and over 220 bird species (123 nesting and recorded during the breeding season species), and 60 species of mammals. "Central Balkan" National Park hosts some of the last existing habitats in Europe of the big rapacious birds, the brown bear, the wolf and the Balkan chamois. The park is of national importance for the conservation of the populations of white-backed woodpecker, the imperial and the golden eagle, the pine-marten, the Ural owl and the hazel hen. There are nine reserves within the Park: "Boatin", "Tsarichina", "Kozya Stena", "Steneto", "Severen Dzhendem", "Peeshti Skali", "Sokolna", "Dzhendema" and "Stara Reka". In total, they cover 28% of the park's territory. "Dzhendema" reserve is also famous for the highest waterfall on the Balkans - "Raysko Praskalo" (124.5 m). "Central Balkan" National Park belongs to the PAN (Protected Areas Network) Parks as an international recognition for its well-managed and preserved wild nature and it is also on the UN List of Representative Protected Areas along with 8 of its reserves.

Nature Parks

Nature parks are areas that include diverse ecosystems with a variety of plant and animal species and their habitats, with typical and remarkable landscapes and natural monuments. They correspond to IUCN's protected areas Category V (Protected Landscape/Seascape). Unlike national parks, within nature parks settlements and resorts are permitted, as well as industrial and other activities, provided they do not pollute the environment. 11 Nature Parks have been established in Bulgaria: "Balgarka", "Vitosha", "Vrachanski Balkan", "Zlatni pyasatsi", "Persina", "Rilski Manastir" (Fig. 3), "Rusenski Lom", "Sinite kamani", "Strandzha" (Fig. 4), "Shumensko plato" and "Belasitsa" (Fig. 5) covering a total area of 273,469 ha. Different types of landownership and a large number of landowners complicate the expansion of their area.

Both types of parks - national and nature parks - encourage the development of sustainable and eco-friendly tourism, educational activities and the traditional livelihoods of the local people.

Natural Monuments and Protected Sites

Natural Monuments (a total 348) and Protected Sites (a total 562) have a smaller area and protect specific outstanding elements of natural landscapes and habitats of rare and endangered species and communities. They correspond generally to those in categories III and IV of IUCN, respectively.

Managed Nature Reserves

Managed Nature Reserves aim to maintain, conserve and restore habitats and species of international, national or local importance. These are currently 35 and are similar to IUCN's category IV.

Natura 2000 protected sites

The EU Directive 92/43/EEC for Protection of the Natural Habitats and Wild Flora and Fauna (briefly the Habitats Directive) and the Council Directive 2009/147/EEC on the Conservation of Wild Birds (the Birds Directive) that set the framework for the EU environmental network Natura 2000 are implemented in Bulgaria through the Biological Diversity Act (2002). The Biodiversity Act regulates the establishment of protected sites for the conservation and maintenance of favourable conservation status of natural habitats

and target species in their natural range. Both directives regulate the establishment of the European Natura 2000 network. In many cases, the networks of protected sites under both Directives partially or completely overlap and they could incorporate protected areas according to the Natural Protected Areas Act. In general, the regimes of the protected sites are generic and there are no significant restrictions. All kinds of human activities can be carried out within Natura 2000 sites, provided they do not destroy habitats that are subject to protection. The national policy for governing and management of the protected areas is implemented by the Ministry of Environment and Water.

The environmental network Natura 2000 comprises 34.5% of the state territory, including 119 Special Protection Areas (SPA) in accordance with the Birds Directive (22.7%) and 234 Sites of Community Importance (SCI) in accordance with the Habitats Directive (30%). 88 habitat types are listed in Annex I of the Biological Diversity Act, 26 of which are priority ones. Annex II of the Habitats Directive includes plant and animal species (other than birds) that are endangered, potentially endangered, rare or endemic. In summary, 25 species of mammals, 10 species of amphibians and reptiles, 25 species of fishes, 36 species of invertebrates and 20 species of plants are part of Annex II of the Biodiversity Act.

OTHER INTERNATIONAL PROTECTED AREAS AND CONSERVATION TYPES

Among the notable international environmental agreements applicable to Bulgarian nature protection the Convention on Biological Diversity, the Convention on Wetlands of International Importance especially as Waterfowl Habitat (Ramsar Convention), the World Heritage Convention and the UNESCO Man and the Biosphere Programme are of special relevance in order to implement actions related to the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity.

Bulgaria is a party to the Ramsar Convention since 1975 and has joined the agreement with 2 of its wetlands, namely "Arkutino" and "Srebarna". Later on the Atanasovsko, Durankulak and Shabla lakes were added to the list. At present, there are 11 Ramsar sites in total. The properties inscribed on the World Heritage List for Bulgaria are 7 cultural sites and 2 natural ones - "Pirin" National Park and "Srebarna" Nature Reserve. The last one is of great importance to the bird migration route Via Pontica.

In compliance with its international obligations, Bulgaria has developed the National Biodiversity Conservation Strategy (2011-2020).

MAIN THREATS TO PROTECTED AREAS AND PREVENTION OPPORTUNITIES IN BULGARIA

Although, in general, the protected areas network in Bulgaria is well developed and it holds very good to excellent preserved biodiversity it is a subject to serious human pressure and threat. The main threats to the nature can be summarized in a few points:

- changes to land use associated with overbuilding, agriculture and others as a result of reducing of natural and semi-natural areas, especially in the Black Sea and the Alpine biogeographic regions;
- overexploitation of natural resources, mainly observed in the forestry sector, where excessive felling is carried out without compliance with the regulations and recommendations;
 - illegal yield (incl. poaching);
 - improper management practices;
 - ecosystems fragmentaion;
 - water pollution;
 - soil erosion;
 - mass tourism.

The prevention of these threats and the measures for reducing their impact are insufficient, due to the lack of effective preservation of protected areas and mostly non-compliance or lack of actual implementation of the Bulgarian and EU legislative norms. All of these circumstances, coupled with low administrative and scientific capacity as well as low engagement of the large public leads to weak and almost lacking conservation of Bulgarian protected areas.

In order to improve the conservation of the protected areas the most urgent steps needed are: most strict compliance with the laws in Bulgaria, making decisions at expert level rather than at political one, and continuous monitoring by the civil society in Bulgaria.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We are very grateful to Rashid Rashid (Sofia, Bulgaria) for the map of the protected areas in Bulgaria.

REFERENCES

Biological Diversity Act (2002). <http://old.europe.bg/upload/docs/CONF_BG_02_03_ad12.pdf>

- Biodiversity Support Program. 1994. Conserving Biological Diversity in Bulgaria: The National Biological Diversity Conservation Strategy⁷. Washington, D.C.: Biodiversity Support Program c/o World Wildlife Fund.
- Birds Directive - Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2009 on the conservation of wild birds (codified version of Directive 79/409/EEC as amended). <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/legislation/birdsdirective/index_en.htm>
- Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (2004) Conference of the Parties Decision VII/28, para. 8. <www.cbd.int/convention/results/?id=7765&l0=PA>
- Dudley N. (Ed.), 2008. Guidelines for Applying Protected Area Management Categories. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN. x + 86 pp.
- Fifth National Report on Biodiversity, Bulgaria 2009-2013. Ministry of Environment and Water of the Republic of Bulgaria. <<https://www.cbd.int/doc/world/bg/bg-nr-05-en.pdf>>
- The Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC - Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora; <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/legislation/habitatsdirective/index_en.htm>
- International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) and United Nations Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre (UNEP-WCMC) (2014) Global Statistics from The World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA): August 2014, UNEP-WCMC, Cambridge.
- Management plan for the National Park “Central Balkan” for the period 2014-2024.
- Management plan for the National Park “Rila” for the period 2014-2024.
- Management plan for the National Park “Pirin”, 2014-2024.
- National Biodiversity Conservation Strategy. <<http://www.strategy.bg/FileHandler.ashx?fileId=496>>.
- Register of protected areas in Bulgaria. Executive Environment Agency (ExEA). Ministry of Environment and Water of the Republic of Bulgaria. <<http://eea.government.bg/zpo/en/>>
- Protected Areas Act, 1998. <http://www3.moew.government.bg/files/file/PNOOP/Acts_in_English/Protected_Areas_Act.pdf>
- Worboys G.L., Lockwood M., Kothari A., Feary S. & Pulsford I. (Eds.), 2015. Protected area governance and management. ANU Press, Canberra, 966 pp.